

TODAY'S HOUSING OPTIONS AND UTILITIES

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Annotation: The content of the article is the current issue of the day, and all the important points are presented for the preparation of the exercises from the regional point of view. Of course, in order to develop the region from the economic and geographical point of view, we need to study the geography of the location of the service centers related to this topic in the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. In this related article, the geography of the primary service branches was studied, and at the present time, the main indicators of the service branches were enriched with statistical information and the main indicators were studied in the new volume.

Key words: Public service, geographical analysis, regional, creation, territory, study, current issue, economic point

The problems of the regional development of public service organizations would be the basis of the geographical analysis. At a certain time, the creation of services in each region can be understood as the connection of regional systems and the regional creation of services. The processes of the regional development of the service corps, which existed at one point in time (modern state), have also started new processes. In the development of the service corps, all the services of the people of the nose have a special importance, if they do not have a special area. The main task of the geography of the public service organization is the clarification of the principles of regional coordination of the service organization.

Yu.G. Saushkin (1973, p. 225-226) in his speech, when he put the regional structure of the service corps, the "points" that could be taken into account, were arranged in accordance with the continuous movement of people. was used in the sense of the full understanding of the public's needs. The factors affecting the regional structure of all systems of public service institutions are economic factors (economic factors of the region, the state, or the economic and geographical location of the population, economic development, and the level of economic development of the region).

Departments of public service provide housing, communal services, maintenance of trade, social awareness, education, medicine, and health care. In daily life, it is necessary to take care of all the parts of the service, which are related to the needs of human beings. For this purpose, in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, in the following years, large-scale works on the development of social networks will be carried out. In the region of the Republic, he served in the areas of public welfare, social welfare, providing medical services to the people, public education, and other aspects of improving the material well-being of the people. In the following years, there will be an opportunity to develop the economic sectors. Through this topic, we will analyze the relevant factors from a geographical point of view and learn together with the problems of regional development of public service organizations of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Housing options and utilities. One of the priorities of the social development program of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is the provision of public housing and communal services. The

people were living in peace and prosperity, and they were building their homes. A large number of jobs are being carried out in these areas. Currently, the people of the republic build 320-362 thousand square meters of housing stock per year. Compared to previous years, this is much more. The majority of the population is working through organizations that are not part of the government. In 2008, according to all sources, 363.7 thousand square meters of residential buildings were constructed in the region of the republic. A total of 301.0 thousand sq.m. So, today, an average person can buy 15.5 sq.m of housing stock per day.

Therefore, in urban areas, the total area of residential housing was 15.4 square meters, while in rural areas it was 15.7 square meters. This is 19.8% higher than the average rate for Uzbekistan. In the following years, in the construction of housing fund, plans are being made to increase the size of the housing fund by 21.5 square meters, taking into account the demographic trends in our country's hot climate, as well as the increase in the volume of bank loans. In the future, it is very important to take advantage of the development of housing facilities in Tashkent and pay special attention to the construction of the housing fund in accordance with the national programs of the people. As such, it is necessary to take care of the problems of water pipes, heating lines, and other sewerage reconstruction problems.

According to the current requirements, 64.5 km of gas pipelines were built in the region of the republic only in 2008, and in the next 2-3 years, 870.8 km of gas networks were built and put into use. A total of 817.6 km of underground railway was built. In the meantime, a water pipeline was built. This year, 67.3 mln cubic meters of water were installed in the pipeline, which increased the efficiency of the pipeline to 49%. However, it is still not acceptable. 385.2 square meters of residential land, 250 km of gas networks, and 270 km of water pipelines are to be provided in the area of like that. In order to improve the level of service to the people of the city, the trolleybus lines were reworked in the city of Nukus, and the tram line was put into operation. In Tórtkúl castle, the expansion of the regional office is also being held in preparation for the construction of sewerage networks in Shomanay district. In addition, the implementation of the housing fund opened the way for the improvement of all municipal departments, as well as for the reconstruction of residential buildings under individual mental care in accordance with modern requirements.

	2017	2018	2019	2020
Republic of Karakalpakistan	19,2	18,0	16,6	16,5
Nukus	21,0	21,2	19,3	19,0
Amiwdaryya	21,6	18,7	16,2	16,0
Beruniy	18,6	18,6	18,5	16,4
Bozataw	-	-	10,1	10,1
Qaraozek	15,1	15,2	12,9	12,9
Kegeyli	15,8	16,1	13,1	13,1
Qon'irat	18,5	18,5	16,4	16,5
Kanlikol	17,2	17,4	15,2	15,3
Moynak	14,3	14,5	13,0	13,0
Nukus region	23,9	24,3	21,2	20,8
Taxiyatas	15,5	11,8	11,8	11,9

Taxtakopir	16,1	16,1	13,5	13,4
Tortkul	19,9	19,7	18,8	18,6
Shimbay	16,2	16,2	12,6	12,7
Shomanay	14,0	14,2	14,3	14,3
Ellikqala	22,3	22,0	17,4	17,2

It is important to note that public service organizations have a relationship with social infrastructure in different literatures. However, the infrastructure (infrastructure, structure-building) is not recognized as a separate part of the economy, but it is the foundation of the complex of conditions necessary for the maintenance of the population. Public service plays an important role in the social construction process. In fact, all material and spiritual wealth was created primarily for the purpose of satisfying human needs. As the demand of the people increases, the content of the service is changing, and the types and forms of the services are increasing.

Currently, the public service corps has already started working. Among them are municipal services, health care, social security, recreation and tourism services, transportation services, housing services, educational services, industrial services, financial services, legal services, communication services, commercial transportation services, etc. All these services are aimed at improving the standard of living of the people. The regional focus of the service centers is determined by the location of the population and its socio-demographic differences.

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